

susceptible high-yielding varieties and increased use of nitrogen fertilizer.

To assess the intensity of bacterial blight, a field trial was conducted during the 1975 kuruvai season (July–October) with four levels of nitrogen (0, 50, 100, and 150 kg N/ha). A variety that was highly susceptible to bacterial blight, Karuna (Co. 33), was grown. The intensity of the disease was recorded during the maximum tillering stage, and the total nitrogen content of healthy and diseased leaves was estimated. The disease severity was significantly less with zero nitrogen, and increased with increasing levels of nitrogen. Severe bacterial blight was observed at 150 kg N/ha. The total nitrogen content of infected leaves was reduced more than that of healthy leaves. Increased grain and straw yields were observed in all treatments except the check. However, the reduction in grain and straw yield at the 150 kg N/ha level was due to the severity of the disease.

Efficacy of certain fungicides in the control of bacterial blight of rice

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Field trials were conducted with certain fungicides to assess their efficacy in controlling bacterial blight of rice caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae*. The trials were conducted in randomized block design in two seasons in 1973–74, the kuruvai (June–September) and the thaladi (November–February), using the susceptible varieties Karuna and IR8, respectively. The treatments were 1) Fytolan, 2) T.F. 130 (thiadiazole compound), 3) Vitavax, 4) Cuman EC, 5) Dithane Z-78, 6) Hinosan, and 7) untreated control. Three applications were made at 55, 65, and 75 days. Significantly less disease incidence was recorded in all treatments than in the untreated check. The lowest disease incidence in both seasons was obtained with T.F. 130, followed by Cuman EC and Fytolan (copper oxychloride). copper oxychloride was not phytotoxic on the two varieties.

Efficacy of certain fungicides in the control of sheath blight

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Sheath blight of rice incited by *Corticium sasakii* Shirai Matsumoto is a serious disease in many ricegrowing areas. With the introduction of high-yielding and high-fertility strains of rice, the disease is becoming more common. To study control measures, the fungicides Benlate W.P., Brassicol W.P., Hinosan EC, Kitazin EC, and Dithane D-14 EC were tested at 0.3 and 0.4 levels under pot culture conditions during kuruvai 1975. ADT 31, a variety susceptible to the disease, was raised in cement pots and then sprayed with the fungicides during the maximum tillering stage. The results showed that the systemic fungicide Benlate most effectively checked the disease, followed by Hinosan and Brassicol. Kitazin was also effective in controlling the disease, but it was phytotoxic at the concentrations tested. Dithane D-14 was ineffective against sheath blight, and phytotoxic to rice plants.

Incidence of sheath rot in rice – a potential problem for Sambalpur, Orissa

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Sheath rot caused by *Acrocyldrium oryzae* Saw. was observed in high-yielding varieties (HYV) grown in and around the Sambalpur ricegrowing areas in 1974 kharif and rabi and again in 1975 kharif. The intensity of the disease in 1974 rabi was higher than that in the preceding or the succeeding kharif. Sheath rot was widely prevalent in the HW and, to a lesser extent, in local tall varieties in farmers' fields. The disease was also noticed in local tall varieties in some ricegrowing areas of the adjacent district, Sundargarh, in 1975 kharif. The choking and sheath rot symptoms with discolored grains were more conspicuous in the HW. The table shows rices that are doing well under sheath rot pressure,

Reactions of varieties to sheath rot at Chiplima (Sambalpur), Orissa, India, in the 1975 kharif.

Designation	Reaction ^{a/}
IR24	R
IR26	R
CR 44-1 20-1	R
RP 825-70-7-1	MR
RP 825-71-4-1	R
RP 884-81-1	R
RP 974-1 12-1-6	R
IR1529-RP6801	R
IR2071-176-1-2-1	R
IR2071-669-3-6-4	MR
IR2071-685-3-5-4	R
CR 93-4-2	R
R 2410	R
Jaya	MR

^{a/}R = resistant; MR = moderately resistant.

Widespread occurrence of leaf scald of rice in Indonesia

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During the 1976 wet season (December–March), leaf scald disease (caused by *Rhynchosporium oryzae*) affected more than 1,000 ha of lowland rice in two districts, Gowa and Takalar, of South Sulawesi province. Bakka, a popular local variety, suffered most, but others, including improved varieties, were also affected.

The disease was observed at all plant stages, from seedling to maturity. Panicles of severely affected mature plants were also affected. The most commonly affected stage was maximum tillering. The disease was generally restricted to the tips of the lower leaves. When the spots were few and isolated, typical leaf scald symptoms were noticed. When the spots coalesced and were in an advanced stage, the symptoms resembled those of bacterial blight. Isolations yielded the leaf scald pathogen.

The disease was also observed in upland rice. It was found in both nitrogen-deficient and fertilized fields, but was more conspicuous in the latter.

Although the disease has previously been noted, this was the first time that large areas were affected in this province. Its present incidence, however, is not alarming. Its spread and incidence would be worth watching in other areas in the future.